

IMPORTANCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL BIOTECHNOLOGY METHODS ON REDUCING PLASTIC POLLUTION

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Abstract. Environmental biotechnology methods play a pivotal role in mitigating the pervasive issue of plastic pollution, offering sustainable solutions to address environmental challenges. This article explores the significance of environmental biotechnology in combating plastic pollution through various approaches such as biodegradation and bioplastics. Biotechnological tools facilitate the degradation of micro (nano) plastics, while bioplastics offer a renewable alternative to conventional plastics, thus reducing environmental impact. Additionally, the role of microbes and catalytic enzymes in controlling plastic pollution is highlighted, emphasizing the multifaceted applications of environmental biotechnology in addressing this global concern.

Keywords: Environmental biotechnology, plastic pollution, micro(nano)plastics, biodegradation, bioplastics, sustainable solutions, microbial degradation, catalytic enzymes.

Introduction. Environmental biotechnology plays a crucial role in protecting nature by conserving biodiversity, enhancing agricultural sustainability, and remediating environmental pollution. Pathak (2014) and Soetan (2011) both highlight the potential of biotechnological methods, such as plant tissue culture and genetically modified crops, in conserving biodiversity and reducing the use of agro-chemicals. Mohanta (2015) further emphasizes the role of biotechnology in bioremediation, particularly in the removal of contaminated materials from the environment. This is supported by Fahmideh (2014), who underscores the use of microorganisms in environmental biotechnology to improve environmental quality, particularly in the areas of wastewater treatment, soil treatment, and treatment of gaseous pollutants. These studies collectively underscore the significant impact of environmental biotechnology in protecting nature.

Importance of environmental biotechnology in reducing plastic pollution. Environmental biotechnology methods play a crucial role in reducing plastic pollution. Silva (2018) and Souza (2021) both highlight the potential of biotechnology tools in facilitating the degradation of micro(nano)plastics, which are particularly challenging to manage. Sharma (2021) emphasizes the importance of bioplastics, which are natural and renewable, in reducing plastic pollution. These bioplastics can be produced from raw materials such as sugarcane, corn starch, and bacteria, and can decompose back

into carbon dioxide. Ghafoor (2022) further underscores the role of biodegradation and biotechnological approaches in controlling plastic pollution on land and in the ocean, particularly through the use of microbes and catalytic enzymes.

Future solutions. Environmental biotechnology methods offer future solutions to plastic pollution by providing innovative ways to manage plastic waste. Biotechnology can contribute to a reduction in plastic waste while enhancing product quality and convenience. It can be used to produce more environmentally friendly polymers and provide a more effective way to deal with plastic waste. Biotechnology may be utilized to create more sustainable polymers and offer a more effective method for managing plastic waste, which could lead to a more sustainable future for our planet.

Anand (2023) reported that, biotechnology can be employed to handle plastic waste in various ways. For instance, researchers have developed a new type of biocatalyst that can degrade polyurethane, significantly reducing its environmental impact. This biocatalyst is composed of enzymes that expedite the degradation of these polymers, presenting a promising solution for reducing the volume of plastic waste that accumulates in landfills and oceans. Biotechnology can also be used to facilitate more effective recycling procedures, increase productivity, reduce manufacturing costs, and transform plastic waste into valuable goods.

Moreover, biotechnology can limit the quantity of garbage that winds up in landfills or bodies of water by disassembling the waste into making it simpler to separate the various forms of plastics. Biotechnology can also be used to produce biodegradable polymers, which naturally decompose over time and have a smaller overall environmental impact. Eventually, using biotechnology, new materials made from waste plastic may be produced, which could replace conventional plastics in various applications and might even be more ecologically friendly.

Biotechnological methods to remove microplastics are also being explored. Microplastics are diverse and highly complex contaminants that transport other contaminants and microbes, posing a major threat to ecosystems and impacting abiotic and biotic components. Biodegradation, incineration, landfilling, and recycling are current methods to remove microplastics, but biotechnological methods are being developed to enhance degradation, such as gene editing tools and bioinformatics. Algae, fungi, and bacteria can play a role in the biodegradation of microplastics, and biotechnological interventions can be used to enhance this process.

In conclusion, environmental biotechnology methods offer future solutions to plastic pollution by providing innovative ways to manage plastic waste, reduce its environmental impact, and produce new materials from waste plastic. The use of biotechnology in plastic waste management is growing in popularity due to its potential to make plastic waste more sustainable, improve efficiency, reduce environmental

impact, and create new materials with distinct features and applications that could replace conventional plastics in various applications.

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